

PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF MANDELIC ACID BY BROMINE WITH TUNGSTIC ACID SOL AS SENSITISER IN ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT OF 254 $\mu\mu$.

By J. C. GHOSH, S. K. BHATTACHARYYA AND K. R. KAR.

A detailed investigation has been made on the oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine with tungstic acid sol as the sensitiser in ultraviolet light of 254 $\mu\mu$. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to bromine and also with respect to mandelic acid. The velocity constant passes through a maximum at $\rho_n 4.05$ and it is independent of the concentration of sodium tungstate so long as the ρ_n is constant. The velocity constant is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by tungstic acid sol. Temperature coefficient is small and the quantum efficiency is more than unity. A mechanism has been suggested.

Ghosh and Purakayastha (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, B, 9, 54) have already shown that bromine reacts with mandelic acid directly only at wave-lengths above 313 $\mu\mu$. In the region below 313 $\mu\mu$ the reaction is a purely sensitised one. Ghosh and Roy (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 32, 158) have studied the photochemical oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine in wave-length 254 $\mu\mu$ with uranyl sulphate as sensitiser. The object of the present investigation was to study the same photochemical oxidation with tungstic acid sol as photosensitiser in wave-length of 254 $\mu\mu$.

The oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine in presence of tungstic acid sol occurs in the dark to a small extent. By adding a very dilute solution of potassium bromide (0.005 M) to the reaction mixture the dark reaction was completely stopped. Ghosh and Purakayastha (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, B, 7, 285; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 8, 361) have shown that the photo-oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine is unimolecular in the absence of KBr and also in presence of a small quantity of KBr; and the length of the dark reaction chain following the primary photo-process in this case is quite considerable. In the presence of excess of KBr it is found, however, that the reaction becomes zero molecular and simultaneously the chain length is also considerably diminished. A small addition of KBr at the start ensures the advantage that the bromine ion, produced during the initial stages of the reaction when the velocity is being measured, does not exert any perceptible retarding effect, if it is very much less than the bromine molecules already present. In the present investigation the reaction was found to be unimolecular.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement was the same as was described by Ghosh and Bhattacharyya in the previous paper (*this issue*, p. 503).

Kahlbaum's extra pure mandelic acid, Merck's extra pure reagent bromine, Merck's pure potassium bromide, sodium tungstate and HCl were used. For making solutions bi-distilled water was used.

The velocity of reaction was found to follow a unimolecular course with respect to bromine, the velocity constant being calculated according to $k = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \log \frac{a}{a-x}$ where a is the initial concen-

tration of bromine in g. mols per litre and x , the change in concentration of bromine in g. mols per litre in time t minutes. The experimental data are recorded in Tables I to VI.

λ =wave-length ; I_{abs} =no. of quanta absorbed by tungstic acid sol per c.c. per second ; θ =temperature ; t =time in minutes ; T_1 =titre difference in c.c. of 0.01*N*-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.29 c.c. of the reaction mixture when exposed to light passing through bromine filter for t minutes ; T_2 =titre difference in c.c. of 0.01*N*-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.29 c.c. of the reaction mixture when exposed to light passing through bromine filter and tungstic acid sol filter in series for t minutes ; T_3 =titre difference in c.c. of 0.01*N*-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.29 c.c. of the reaction mixture due to reaction only for 254 μ in t minutes ; and γ =quantum efficiency.

TABLE I.

$\lambda = 254 \mu$. Mandelic acid = 0.25 <i>M</i> . KBr = 0.005 <i>M</i> .		Na-tungstate = 0.025 <i>M</i> . $I_{abs} = 35.4 \times 10^{-12}$.			HCl = 0.0363 <i>M</i> . $\theta = 30^\circ$. $p_H = 4.05$.	
Conc. of total Br ₂ .	t .	T_1 .	T_2 .	T_3 .	$k \times 10^{-4}$.	γ .
0.044 <i>M</i>	200	0.82	0.55	0.27	5.6	6.4
0.028	200	0.62	0.45	0.17	5.5	4.3
0.02	200	0.40	0.28	0.12	5.5	3.1

Effect of varying the Concentration of Bromine.

From Table I we see that the velocity constant is independent of the initial concentration of bromine.

TABLE II.			TABLE III.			TABLE IV.			TABLE V.		
$I_{abs} = 1.8 \times 10^{12}$. Total Br ₂ = 0.026 <i>M</i> . Other conditions same as in Table I.			Total Br ₂ = 0.003 <i>M</i> . Other conditions same as in Table I.			Mandelic acid = 0.31 <i>M</i> . Total Br ₂ = 0.032. Other conditions same as in Table I.			Total Br ₂ = 0.032 <i>M</i> . Other conditions same as in Table I.		
Mandelic acid.	$k \times 10^{-4}$.	γ .	p_H .	$k \times 10^{-4}$.	γ .	Tungstate.	$k \times 10^{-4}$.	$I_{abs} \times 10^{-12}$	Mandelic acid.	$k \times 10^{-4}$.	γ .
0.25 <i>M</i>	1.4	4.5	5.52	1.6	1.5	0.125 <i>M</i>	1.2	11.2	0.31 <i>M</i>	1.3	2.3
0.31	1.7	5.3	5.4	2.0		0.025	1.3	12.1	"	4.3	
0.38	2.2	6.9	4.05	5.7		0.0375	1.2	11.2	0.42	3.0	
0.45	2.5	7.7	2.66	0.9				12.1	"	5.6	
			2.32	0.8							

From Table II, we see that the velocity constant is proportional to the concentration of mandelic acid.

Effect of varying the p_H of the Solution.—The velocity constant passes through a maximum at $p_H = 4.05$.

Effect of varying the Concentration of Sodium Tungstate.—From Table IV we see that the velocity constant is independent of the concentration of sodium tungstate so long as the p_H is kept constant.

Effect of varying the Intensity.—It is evident from TABLE V that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by tungstic acid sol.

TABLE VI.

Effect of varying the temperature.

$\lambda = 254 \mu\mu$. $I_{abs} = 8.8 \times 10^{11}$. $p_H = 4.05$. $v =$ Temperature coefficient for 10° rise. Total $Br_2 = 0.032M$.

Mandelic acid.	Tungstate.	HCl.	Total Br_2 .	KBr.	$k \times 10^{-4}$		v
					$\theta = 30^\circ$	$\theta = 40^\circ$	
0.31 M	0.025 M	0.0383 M	0.032 M	0.005 M	1.7	2.3	1.35

DISCUSSION.

The reaction has the following characteristics:—

(a) The velocity of reaction is unimolecular with respect to bromine and also with respect to mandelic acid; (b) there is no induction period; (c) the velocity constant is independent of the concentration of sodium tungstate so long as the hydrogen-ion concentration is kept constant; (d) the velocity constant passes through a maximum at $p_H 4.05$; (e) the temperature coefficient is small; (f) the velocity constant is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by tungstic acid sol; (g) the quantum efficiency lies between 1 and 7.

The fact that the velocity constant is proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation and not to its square root leads to the conclusion that bromine atoms are not the active reagents. The simplest mechanism of reaction may be imagined as follows.

The surface concentrations of both bromine and mandelic acid on tungstic acid micelle are proportional to their respective bulk concentrations. A centre of reaction on the tungstic acid micelles produced by absorption of a quantum of radiation is reduced by a neighbouring mandelic acid molecule. The reduced tungstic acid is in its turn oxidised by a molecule of bromine. When the stationary state is reached, the velocity of oxidation of mandelic acid is equal to the velocity of reduction of bromine and each in its turn is proportional to the respective surface concentration. The observation that one quantum of radiation can transform several molecules can only be explained on the basis that the energy-rich product of reaction may bring into activation new centres of reaction on the surface of the tungstic acid micelles.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY, DACCA, AND
THE INDIAN INSTITUTE OF
SCIENCE, BANGALORE.

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